

Exploring artificial diets for the laboratory rearing of *Sirex noctilio* late-instar larvae: a qualitative study

Elmarie van der Merwe¹, Bernard Slippers² and Gudrun Dittrich-Schröder^{1*}

¹ Department of Zoology and Entomology, Forestry and Agricultural Biotechnology Institute (FABI), University of Pretoria, Pretoria, 0002, South Africa

² Department of Biochemistry, Genetics and Microbiology, Forestry and Agricultural Biotechnology Institute (FABI), University of Pretoria, Pretoria, 0002, South Africa

* Correspondence: gudrun.dittrich@fabi.up.ac.za

Telephone number: +271204206753

Fax number: +27124203960

* CRediT Contributor Role Taxonomy

Elmarie van der Merwe: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review and editing

Bernard Slippers: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Writing – review and editing

Gudrun Dittrich-Schroder: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Methodology, project administration, Resources, Supervision, Writing – review and editing

* ORCID ID: Elmarie van der Merwe	https://orcid.org/0009-0003-5345-0101
Bernard Slippers	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1491-3858
Gudrun Dittrich-Schröder	https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5700-6276

Abstract

Sirex noctilio (Hymenoptera: Siricidae) is a well-known pest in commercial pine plantations in the Southern Hemisphere. It is difficult to study the development of the woodwasp since it spends most of its life inside the host tree. Researchers have developed extraction methods, such as splitting logs or sawing thin sections of a log, to examine internal parts of the host tree and study *S. noctilio*, but these methods are labour-intensive and time-consuming. Artificial diets have been

developed for many insects allowing researchers to observe all life stages of an insect, as well as to enable broader experimentation with these life stages. The aim of this study was therefore to initiate the development of an artificial diet for *S. noctilio* larvae and to evaluate the suitability of this diet for the laboratory rearing of *S. noctilio*. Three artificial diets were qualitatively tested for the rearing of *S. noctilio* late-instar larvae, which included (A) modified versions of a commercially produced *Anoplophora glabripennis* (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) diet, (B) agar-based pine shavings/sawdust diet, and (C) wheat/rice diet used to rear *Deladenus siricidicola* (Tylenchida: Neotylenchidae). In addition, different techniques for rearing larvae on the artificial diets were evaluated. The results showed that the original *A. glabripennis* diet, including some modified versions, worked the best to rear *S. noctilio* larvae. Compared to other methods, rearing larvae inside Petri dishes was most suitable. The method developed in this study shows potential to reduce labour and space for conducting research on *S. noctilio*, and forms the basis for the establishment of a laboratory reared population.

Key words: larval development; woodwasp; *Amylostereum areolatum*; *Anoplophora glabripennis*.

1. Introduction

Rearing insect pests on an artificial diet can enhance the understanding of the pest's biology and nutritional requirements, which can be exploited for development of pest management strategies (Pinto *et al.*, 2019). In addition, pest management strategies such as biological control and genetic pest management depend on artificial diets to mass-rear sufficient numbers of the control agent for environmental release (Sahayaraj & Balasubramanian, 2009; Leftwich *et al.*, 2021). In biological control programs the natural enemy of the target insect pest is mass-reared (Sahayaraj & Balasubramanian, 2009), while in genetic pest management strategies a genetically modified version of the insect pest itself is mass-reared (Leftwich *et al.*, 2021). Many artificial diets have been developed for various insect pests, such as wood-boring beetles (Saunders &

Knoke, 1967; De Viedma *et al.*, 1985; Rogers *et al.*, 2002; Keena, 2005; Cooperband *et al.*, 2016; Sharma *et al.*, 2016), however, none have been developed for wood-boring wasps.

Sirex noctilio Fabricius (Hymenoptera: Siricidae) is an invasive wood-boring wasp of economic importance in the Southern Hemisphere, including South Africa (Ciesla, 2003; Hurley *et al.*, 2007). Currently, rearing of *S. noctilio* involves either allowing ovigerous females to oviposit into pine logs stored in cages, or placing already infested pine logs from plantations in cages while waiting for adults to emerge (Madden, 1981; Yousuf *et al.*, 2014; Fernández Ajó *et al.*, 2015). The time it takes for adults to emerge is usually one year, but can take up to two years under colder conditions (Hoebeke *et al.*, 2005). During this developmental period in the host, the wasp's development is obscured (Ryan & Hurley, 2012). The current rearing strategy for *S. noctilio* is not feasible for development and implementation of new management strategies, such as genetic pest management strategies, emphasising the need for an artificial diet.

The symbiotic white rot fungus of *S. noctilio*, *Amylostereum areolatum* (Chaillet ex Fr.) Boidin (Russulales: *Amylostereaceae*), plays an important role in the larval nutrition of the wasp (Madden, 1981; Thompson *et al.*, 2013; Thompson *et al.*, 2014). *Sirex noctilio* adults do not feed and survive on stored fat reserves (Hoebeke *et al.*, 2005), while larvae are xylophagous (Gruner & Thompson, 2021). However, larvae are unable to directly digest xylem and require *A. areolatum* to externally break down recalcitrant lignocellulosic compounds before nutrients can be absorbed (Thompson *et al.*, 2014). To aid the establishment of *A. areolatum*, *S. noctilio* produces a phytotoxic mucus (Coutts, 1969b). The fungal-mucus complex is what eventually kills the host tree (Spradbery, 1973). The significance of the *Sirex-Amylostereum* symbiotic relationship in nature may also apply to artificial environments. Therefore, it is important to investigate the role of *A. areolatum* in *S. noctilio* larval nutrition on an artificial diet.

In this study, we aimed to develop an artificial diet to enable rearing of late-instar *S. noctilio* larvae. The objective was to qualitatively compare various artificial diets and approaches for suitability of rearing late-instar *S. noctilio* larvae, extracted from infested pine logs. This study is the first to report on various artificial diets tested on *S. noctilio* larvae.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Pine log supply and maintenance

Sirex noctilio infested *Pinus* sp. logs (\pm 80cm in length, 10-35 cm in diameter) were collected from plantations in two climatically different regions in South Africa, namely Western Cape (winter rainfall, *P. radiata*) and Mpumalanga (summer rainfall, *P. patula*). Three batches (\pm 75-90 logs per batch) were collected from each region between March 2021 and March 2023 (Table S1, Supporting Information). The pine logs were stored during different time points in an outdoor netted cage at the Forestry and Agricultural Biotechnology Institute (FABI) Biocontrol Facility of the University of Pretoria (25°45'09.4"S 28°15'22.3"E). The outdoor netted cage consisted of two layers (Figure 1, A), where the first layer was 100 % Polyolefin with 29 % porosity (Xsect Xtra, Svensson, Sweden) and the second layer was 80 % black net (Greenhouse Products [Pty] Ltd, Dynatrade, South Africa).

Large pine logs were stored upright (Figure 1, A) whereas smaller pine logs were cross-stacked and occasionally rotated (Figure 1, B). The logs were sprayed with water every day for 10 minutes to maintain moisture levels inside the logs for optimal larval development. As an additional measure to limit moisture loss inside the logs, all exposed ends of logs were painted with a non-toxic waterproof sealer (Watershield clear, Atlas Paints, Pretoria, South Africa).

2.2 Extraction of larvae and pupae

Larvae and pupae were extracted by splitting *P. patula* logs from Mpumalanga (Table S1, Batch 1 and 2 from Mpumalanga) using a hand operated MAC AFRIC 10 ton hydraulic log splitter (Adendorff, South Africa) until the thinnest manageable piece remained (Figure 1, C). Larvae and pupae were extracted using soft plastic forceps and transferred to a Petri dish (60 mm, JP Last Plastic Products, Roodepoort, South Africa) (Figure 1, D) inside a dark box.

2.3 Confirmation of *Amylostereum areolatum* identity

The symbiotic relationship between *S. noctilio* and *A. areolatum* is important for larval nutrition (Thompson *et al.*, 2014). To confirm that the fungal culture to be include in the artificial diets was

A. areolatum, a culture of the fungus (CMW 40871) was grown on malt extract agar (MEA) as reported in Mlonyeni *et al.* (2018). CMW 40871 was isolated from the mycangium of *Sirex noctilio* collected in Australia. Two *A. areolatum* mycelial samples were amplified following the protocol reported in Fitza *et al.* (2016). The identity of the isolates was confirmed by performing Basic Local Alignment Search Tool nucleotide (BLASTn) analyses with the obtained sequences against the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) nucleotide database (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi> accessed on 08 October 2021).

2.4 Development of artificial diets for *Sirex noctilio* larvae

Three artificial diets developed for *S. noctilio* larvae were a continuation of previous preliminary work conducted in FABI, together with new innovations. Diet A and B are based on previous work, while Diet C is a previously defined diet that has never been tested on *S. noctilio*. Due to the long life cycle of *S. noctilio*, the survival rate of larvae was not the only factor when evaluating the diets. This study adopted a qualitative approach, focusing on the larvae's response to the diets and evaluating the practicality of these diets for future mass rearing. The aim was to find a diet that is (i) affordable, (ii) easy to produce, (iii) sustainable (does not need to be replaced regularly during rearing), and (iv) is suitable for *S. noctilio* development. Prior to adding larvae onto each diet, larvae were surface sterilised by rinsing them in 50% ethanol for two seconds. The recipe with alterations and rearing technique for each diet are described below.

2.4.1 Diet A

Diet A (as reported in Van der Merwe *et al.* (2023)) is based on an artificial diet for the Asian long-horned beetle (ALB), *Anoplophora glabripennis* (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae), originally developed by Keena (2005), and currently mass produced by Natural Resources Canada (NRCan) (Table S2 Supporting information). Preliminary work (Dr. Josephine Queffelec and Ms. Leandri Klynsmith, personal communication) showed some success with rearing *S. noctilio* larvae on the NRCan prepared ALB diet. For this work, the prepared diet ('Diet A-NRC') and dry ingredients were ordered. The dry ingredients allowed the recipe to be customised, which included removing preservatives (sorbic acid, methyl paraben, and sodium propionate) to allow *A. areolatum* to

grow and adjusting the recipe method according to equipment available. The original five ingredient groups from the NRCan recipe were kept the same, and three new ingredient groups were added (Group 6-8). Pine sawdust (Group 7) was obtained by abrading the sapwood of a *P. patula* log from the outdoor netted cage using a Metabo BAE 75 belt sander (75 x 533 mm, 1010W). The four main changes made to the diet are described below.

(i) Diet A1

The full ingredient quantities in the NRCan recipe, excluding the preservatives sorbic acid, methyl paraben, and sodium propionate, were used and mixed.. Agar was added to autoclaved distilled water and microwaved until the agar was completely dissolved (± 15 min). After the agar had cooled to ± 40 ° C, wheatgerm oil was added. The cooled agar mixture was added to the dry ingredients and mixed with an electric hand mixer (Kenwood 280W) for 20 sec. A heaped tablespoon of diet was scooped into sterile Petri dishes (60 mm, JP Last Plastic Products, Roodepoort, South Africa) before the diet solidified, after which half of the Petri dishes had autoclaved pine shavings (± 2 g) sprinkled over the diet surface. The Petri dishes were left to cool for 24 hours in a laminar flow hood with lids slightly open. Thereafter, each Petri dish was inoculated with a 5 mm x 5 mm agar plug from an *A. areolatum* (CMW 40871) culture grown on MEA (20 g malt, 30 g purified agar in 1 L distilled water). Petri dishes were sealed with PARAFILM "M" Laboratory film (Pechiney Plastic Packaging, Inc., Chicago, USA) and placed in a cake saver (9.5 L ADDISWARE, South Africa) inside an incubator at 25 ± 1 ° C, 52 ± 2 % r.h. The diet was incubated for at least seven days to allow sufficient time for *A. areolatum* to grow before use.

(ii) Diet A2

The same procedure as Diet A1 was followed, except the ingredient quantities were halved and the raw wheat germ was microwaved for 30 sec before being added to all the dry ingredients. Group 6 was prepared by dissolving streptomycin sulfate salt (0.4 g, Sigma-Aldrich) in SABAX pour water (3 ml) and added to the agar after it had been microwaved and cooled to ± 40 ° C.

(iii) Diet A3

The ingredient quantities were divided by 16, except for the distilled water, which was reduced to 150 ml. Agar was added to distilled water and autoclaved. All dry ingredients from Group 1 (excluding raw wheat germ) and Group 2 (including all preservatives) were mixed. The raw wheat germ was microwaved for 30 sec and added to the Group 1 and 2 ingredient mixture. Group 4 and 5 ingredients were mixed, followed by Group 3 ingredients and lastly Group 6 ingredients (as described in Diet A2). After the autoclaved agar cooled down to $\pm 40^{\circ}\text{C}$, Group 3 and 6 were added to the bottle. The agar mixture was added to the Group 1 and 2 ingredients and mixed with an electric hand mixer for 10 sec. Thereafter, the Group 4 and 5 ingredient mixture was added and mixed with an electric hand mixer for 10 sec. Lastly, Group 7 was added to the bowl and mixed in with a spoon. A heaped tablespoon of diet was scooped into Petri dishes (60 mm) and left to cool for 30 min in a laminar flow hood with lids slightly open until condensation subsided. As with Diet A1 and A2, each Petri dish was inoculated with *A. areolatum*, wrapped in Parafilm, and placed in a cake saver inside a dark incubator at $25 \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$, $52 \pm 2\%$ r.h, for at least seven days.

(iv) Diet A4

As reported in Van der Merwe *et al.* (2023).

2.4.1.1 Exploration of rearing methods for larvae and pupae on Diet A

Diet A was evaluated in (i) Petri dishes (60 mm), (ii) Falcon tubes (50 ml, Lasec, Cape Town, South Africa), (iii) small pieces of *P. patula* logs (± 12 mm long and ± 9 mm in diameter), and (iv) rolled printing paper (Typek, Lithotech, Springs, South Africa) (Figure 1, E - G). With method (i) the Petri dish method, a trench was made in the diet (about the size of the larva/pupa) using a sterile surgical blade (size 24, Huaian Guangda Medical Instruments Co., Ltd., Huaian City, China), which was close to the *A. areolatum* agar plug in Diet A1-A3. A larva/pupa was placed inside the trench, and some were completely covered with the diet to better simulate natural conditions. The Petri dishes used for Diet A-NRC and Diet A4 were aerated by puncturing the lid twice on opposite sides using a heated hypodermic needle (21G x $1\frac{1}{2}$ " , 0.8 x 40 mm, Lysa®, South Africa). All Petri

dishes were wrapped in Parafilm (Figure 1, E). For method (ii), Falcon tubes were filled with Diet A-NRC (30 ml) and a hole was made in the diet (± 8 cm deep) using a chopstick sterilised with 70 % ethanol. A larva/pupa was placed inside the hole, whereafter it was sealed with diet and the lid of the tube was loosely closed (Figure 1, E). Petri dishes and Falcon tubes were stored in cake savers (9.5 L ADDISWARE, South Africa) inside a dark incubator at $25 \pm 1^\circ \text{C}$, $52 \pm 2\%$ r.h.

Method (iii) and (iv), the log and paper roll method, were designed to aid the development of pupae to adults. For method (iii) holes of varying sizes and depths were drilled into small pieces of *P. patula* logs (± 12 mm long and ± 9 mm in diameter) using a hand operated drill (SBE 570 R electronic, AEG Power Tools, Germany). Holes were made on top of the log and on the sides (Figure 1, F). Pupae were placed inside the holes with their heads facing towards the opening and sealed with a small amount of Diet A-NRC. The log was placed in a plastic aerated container and sprayed with distilled water, using a spray bottle (500 ml, Crazy Plastics, South Africa), 3-5 times a week. The aerated containers were made from plastic containers (16 x 16 x 16 cm) with a hole cut out in each lid (13 x 13 cm) and replaced with a fine plastic mesh using a glue gun. Method (iv) involved wrapping a pupa in printing paper (rolled about 4 times) and securing the end of the paper roll with Parafilm (Figure 1, G). The open ends of the paper roll were sealed with Diet A-NRC. The wrapped pupae were placed in aerated Petri dishes (60 mm). The aerated containers, and Petri dishes with wrapped pupae, were placed in a dark incubator at $25 \pm 1^\circ \text{C}$, $52 \pm 2\%$ r.h.

2.4.2 Diet B

Diet B is based on previous work (Termer, 2014) where different pine woodchip treatments, inoculated with *A. areolatum* and distilled water, were tested in order to develop an artificial diet for *S. noctilio* larvae. Diet B used a similar approach to enable growth of *A. areolatum* on an agar and pine shaving/sawdust mixture, to potentially serve as a cheap, simple, and quick diet for *S. noctilio* larvae.

(i) Diet B1

Malt extract agar was made by adding 20 g of MEA and 25 g of purified agar to 1 L of distilled water in a Schott Duran bottle (Duran® Products, Germany) and autoclaved. After the MEA media

had cooled down to $\pm 40^{\circ}\text{C}$, streptomycin sulfate salt (0.4 g) was prepared and added to the liquid agar as described in Diet A3 (Group 6) above. Autoclaved pine shavings (50 g) obtained from sawed *P. patula* logs were added to the MEA media. Under a laminar flow hood the mixture was poured into Petri dishes (60 mm) filling them halfway, and left to cool overnight with lids slightly open. Thereafter, each Petri dish was inoculated with an *A. areolatum* agar plug (5 mm x 5 mm). Petri dishes were sealed with Parafilm and placed in a cake saver inside a dark incubator at $25 \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$, $52 \pm 2\%$ r.h.

(ii) Diet B2

The same procedure was followed as in Diet B1, however, the MEA media was halved (10 g of MEA and 12.5 g of purified agar to 500 L of distilled water) and pine sawdust (50 g) was added. Sawdust was made as described in Diet A (Group 7) above. The sawdust was autoclaved three times in a Schott Duran bottle before use.

2.4.2.1 Rearing of larvae and pupae on Diet B

Similar to rearing larvae and pupae on Diet A, Petri dishes with diet inoculated with *A. areolatum* were incubated for at least seven days at 25°C prior to adding larvae. A trench was made in the diet using a sterile surgical blade near the *A. areolatum* agar plug. A larva/pupa was placed inside the trench, and some were covered with diet. Petri dishes were wrapped in Parafilm and placed in a cake saver inside a dark incubator at $25 \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$, $52 \pm 2\%$ r.h.

2.4.3 Diet C

Diet C was originally used to mass rear *Deladenus siricidicola* (Tylenchida: Neotylenchidae), the biological control agent of *S. noctilio*, at the FABI Biocontrol Facility. The diet consisted of 30 % brown rice (Tastic Rice, South Africa) and 70 % wheat (Lion, pearled whole wheat stampkoring, South Africa) mixture that facilitate the growth of *A. areolatum*, which is the main food source for *D. siricidicola*. This diet showed potential to be a cost-effective alternative for rearing *S. noctilio* larvae in the presence of *A. areolatum*. The prepared diet was supplied by the FABI Biocontrol Facility to conduct this work and transferred into eight individual clear plastic vials (10 ml). Four vials had the plain rice/wheat diet and the remaining four had the rice/wheat diet mixed

with pine sawdust (Figure 1, H – I). Each vial was inoculated with an *A. areolatum* agar plug (5 mm x 5 mm).

2.4.3.1 Rearing of larvae and pupae on Diet C

A larva/pupa was placed underneath ± 2 cm of diet. The vials were aerated by puncturing the lid five times with a heated hypodermic needle. Vials containing diet were placed in a cake saver inside a dark incubator at 25 ± 1 ° C, 52 ± 2 % r.h.

2.5 Determining the conditions for *Amylostereum areolatum* growth in an artificial laboratory environment

From Termer (2014) the question remained as to why *A. areolatum* was unable to grow on the moist pine wood chips. Determining the conditions for *A. areolatum* growth on pine sawdust in an artificial laboratory environment might aid future rearing of *S. noctilio*. Therefore, autoclaved pine sawdust dampened with SABAX pour water was placed in two Petri dishes (30 mm, JP Last Plastic Products, Roodepoort, South Africa). In one of the Petri dishes, phytotoxic mucus obtained from the mucus reservoir in a dissected adult female (as seen in Spradbery, 1973), was mixed into the pine sawdust. Both Petri dishes were inoculated with an *A. areolatum* agar plug (5 mm x 5 mm) and kept at room temperature in the dark.

3. Results

3.1 Pine log supply and maintenance

The outdoor netted cage conditions, daily watering and waterproof sealing of the log ends was conducive to *S. noctilio* development and emergence.

3.2 Confirmation of *Amylostereum areolatum* identity

A 716 bp fragment of the mtSSU rDNA was successfully amplified and sequenced for both samples. The consensus sequences BLASTed to “*Amylostereum areolatum* isolate M1 small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence; mitochondrial” (accession number OL323051.1)

with a percentage sequence identity of 100.00 % and an E-value of 0.0, confirming that the strain used was *A. areolatum*.

3.3 Development of artificial diets for *Sirex noctilio* larvae and pupae

Considering all versions of the three artificial diets evaluated in this study (Table 1), Diet A3, Diet A4, and Diet A-NRC, were the most suitable for rearing *S. noctilio* larvae, due to their affordability, ease of production, absence of fungal contamination, suitability for long-term use, and ability to support larval development.

3.3.1 Diet A

All versions of Diet A, except pre-made Diet A-NRC, were cost efficient to produce. In Diet A4, where the ingredients of the original NRCan recipe were reduced the most (divided by 32), ± 30 Petri dishes filled with diet were produced, of which each larva (depending on age) required about ¼ of the diet in a Petri dish. Diet A took two to three and a half hours to make and was easy to prepare. Regarding contamination, Diet A1 became contaminated with fungal growth (mold) within two days after the diet was produced (during *A. areolatum* establishment), and the contamination constantly needed to be cut out and removed with a sterile surgical blade (Figure 1, J). Despite removing contamination, after seven days the contamination spread over the whole diet surface and adversely affected larval survival. Due to the methods used in Diet A2, the amount of contamination after the diet was produced (prior to adding larvae), was considerably less, however, fungal contamination appeared after seven days and was unable to be contained by day ten. No fungal contamination was visible on Diet A3 (including *A. areolatum*), Diet A4, and Diet A-NRC prior and during larval rearing.

A total of 20 larvae and 14 pupae were reared across Diet A using Petri dishes, Falcon tubes, pine logs with holes, and rolled printing paper. For six larvae that transitioned to pre-pupae, the average developmental rate from larva to pre-pupae was 5 days. The average time from pupation to emergence was 17 days. Due to fungal contamination on Diet A1 and Diet A2 (and limited larvae available), larvae were moved between Diet A1 and Diet A2 for Diet A-NRC, Diet A3, and Diet A4. *Amylostereum areolatum* grew well on both Diet A1 and Diet A2, however, the fungus

would grow over larvae in trenches and adversely affected larval survival (Figure 1, K). Rearing larvae in Petri dishes was the most preferred method. However, larvae often moved out of the trench and covering larvae with diet adversely affected survival, since they would start to swell and ceased development (Figure 1, L). Larval feeding activity on Diet A was not clear, however, small 'balls' of diet were observed near larvae and were thought to be larval frass (Figure 1, M).

The drawback of rearing larvae inside Petri dishes was that *S. noctilio* adults would mostly emerge with deformed wings (Figure 1, N). Larvae and pupae reared inside Falcon tubes did not survive due to swelling. Some adult wasps successfully emerged from the log holes covered with diet, however, these individuals also had deformed wings. None of the pupae wrapped in paper emerged, resulting in pupae decomposing and fungal overgrowth on the diet and paper (Figure 1, O).

3.3.2 Diet B

A total of 23 larvae and 5 pupae were reared on Diet B. Diet B was the cheapest to produce and took about two hours to prepare. It was better to use pine sawdust (Diet B2) than pine shavings (Diet B1), since pine shavings sank to the bottom of the Petri dish before the diet solidified. The drawback of Diet B was that it had very high levels of both fungal and bacterial contamination after adding larvae. A variety of fungi and bacteria were observed (Figure 1, P), usually originating from the trench larvae were placed in. Contamination could not be contained, and became excessive after ten days, which adversely affected larval survival. Larvae that were placed on the diet surface or covered with diet also became swollen, as described above in Diet A. *Amylostereum areolatum* established well on Diet B, but adversely affected survival of larvae that were in very close proximity, due to overgrowth of the fungus onto the larvae (also seen in Diet A). Contamination could not be controlled by cutting out contaminated pieces of diet with a sterile surgical blade.

3.3.3 Diet C

Diet C was the second least expensive to produce, and was prepared in about three hours. *Amylostereum areolatum* grew well on both variations of Diet C, however, contamination levels by other fungi were high (Figure 1, Q). Fungal contamination inside the vials became excessive

within seven days and could not be contained (Figure 1, Q). Diet C was not ideal for larval rearing, since the diet hardened in the vials, which made it difficult to extract larvae. A single, deformed adult male emerged from the diet (Figure 1, R).

3.4 Determining conditions for *Amylostereum areolatum* growth on pine sawdust

Amylostereum areolatum did not grow past the agar plug that was placed inside the Petri dish without the phytotoxic mucus. In contrast, *A. areolatum* established on pine sawdust that came in contact with the phytotoxic mucus. However, the addition of the phytotoxic mucus resulted in contamination by other fungi.

4. Discussion

In this study, initial steps were taken to develop an artificial diet for *S. noctilio*. The diet produced by Natural Recourses Canada for the Asian long-horned beetle (Diet A-NRC), including its modified versions (Diet A3 and Diet A4), showed the highest potential for future applications in *S. noctilio* rearing. These above-mentioned diets were most suitable due to low production cost, an easy preparation process, low maintenance requirement, and the ability to support *S. noctilio* development. However, all three above-mentioned diets contained preservatives, which prevented the growth of *S. noctilio*'s fungal symbiont, *A. areolatum*. Without preservatives in the diet, fungal contamination became excessive (as seen in Diet A1, A2, B1, and B2). Various species of ambrosia beetles have similar symbiotic relationships with fungi as *S. noctilio*, and sawdust-based artificial diets for ambrosia beetles contain no antimicrobial agents, except for bacterial antibiotics, such as streptomycin and tetracycline (French & Roeper, 1972; Biedermann *et al.*, 2009; Castrillo *et al.*, 2011; Menocal *et al.*, 2017). Fungal contamination in ambrosia beetle diets is problematic, but beetles are able to complete their life cycle (Lake Maner *et al.*, 2013). By contrast, fungal contamination adversely affected the development and survival of *S. noctilio* larvae.

Despite the absence of *A. areolatum*, *S. noctilio* larvae developed and emerged on the artificial diets. The ability of *S. noctilio* to survive without its fungal symbiont is likely due to the nutrients in the artificial diet being in a digestible form, which removes the need for digestion by *A.*

areolatum. However, *A. areolatum* may be required during certain stages of the rearing process of *S. noctilio* to ensure that it is transferred between life stages to more accurately reflect wild-type population characteristics during experiments.

A possible solution to incorporate *A. areolatum* during rearing may be to inoculate the phytotoxic mucus on a small area of the artificial diet. In this study, it was shown that the phytotoxic mucus was beneficial to the establishment of *A. areolatum* on pine sawdust in an artificial laboratory environment. *Amylostereum areolatum* is considered a weak pathogen and therefore requires the phytotoxic mucus to support fungal growth in living trees (Coutts, 1969a,b). It is possible that the phytotoxic mucus may create a suitable environment for *A. areolatum* to establish on an artificial diet with antifungal agents. Further investigation into the role of the phytotoxic mucus for the incorporation of *A. areolatum* during rearing of *S. noctilio* should be considered in future.

Sirex noctilio larvae displayed unnoticeable feeding behaviour. However, a type of frass was observed, indicating that *S. noctilio* most likely consumed the diet. The frass produced by *S. noctilio* larvae, when feeding in the host tree, is not considered 'true frass' since the wood material (digested by *A. areolatum*) is not directly ingested, but rather squeezed by larval mandibles to release the trapped liquid with nutrients (Thompson *et al.*, 2013; Thompson *et al.*, 2014). In this case, frass is the pulped wood material that is externally passed along the underside of the larva, whereafter it mixes with a small amount of larval excrement near the anus, and packed tightly behind the larva in the tunnel (Thompson *et al.*, 2013; Thompson *et al.*, 2014). Therefore, the 'diet balls' observed in this study might be due to squeezed diet that was released by larval mandibles after ingestion of the liquid contents. In future, it will be beneficial to weigh *S. noctilio* larvae during rearing to track larval weight gain, which could also indicate acquisition of nutrients without ingestion.

We found that the development of *S. noctilio* larvae and pupae were adversely affected when covered with the artificial diet. This may likely be due to a larger surface of the larva coming in contact with the high moisture content inside the diet, which is also supported by studies showing that *S. noctilio* struggled to survive in moist wood (Coutts & Dolezal, 1965). *Sirex noctilio* larvae developed when placed on the diet surface in a Petri dish.

Many *S. noctilio* adults had deformed wings after emerging in Petri dishes. Similarly, deformed wings were reported in the dragon fly, *Pantala flavescens* (Anisoptera: Libellulidae), after an individual struggled to fully emerge from its exuviae (empty pupal exoskeleton) (Andrew & Patankar, 2010). When winged insects emerge from exuviae, wing expansion is achieved by pumping hemolymph into the wing veins followed by hardening of the wings (White & Ewer, 2016). In addition, the new exoskeleton of adults is soft and rapidly hardens after emergence (White & Ewer, 2010). Therefore, it is important for unfurling wings and the adult exoskeleton to be in the correct orientation and have sufficient space, in order to fully expand and attain their natural shape. Based on the above-mentioned information, the deformed wings of *S. noctilio* observed in this study are likely due to incomplete expansion of the wings after adult emergence. During the molting process of *S. noctilio* in the Petri dish, pupae would roll onto their sides or against the Petri dish edge, which prevented wings from fully expanding and hardening in the correct shape. Similarly, adults that emerged from pupae reared in logs had deformed wings, likely due to the underdeveloped wings of pupae being accidentally folded when placed inside the log holes. The complete deformation observed in the adult male reared on Diet C, is a result of the newly emerged adult being bent over a rice grain, which caused the exoskeleton to harden in that position. The deformation of *S. noctilio* observed during this study stresses the importance of positioning pupae in the correct orientation during rearing.

The artificial diet developed in this study meets the basic requirements for rearing *S. noctilio*, however, there are areas that should be further investigated and optimised. Insects require macro- and micronutrients in the correct proportion for healthy development and reproduction (Woods *et al.*, 2020; Morales-Ramos *et al.*, 2023). The carcass milling technique (CMT), also known as ‘carcass analysis’, can help to improve the formulation of an artificial diet for *S. noctilio* by determining its specific nutrient requirements (Zapata *et al.*, 2005; Ngomane *et al.*, 2022). The technique is based on the principle that a healthy insect has the same nutrient composition as its food source (Lindig *et al.*, 1981; Morales-Ramos *et al.*, 2023). Another important factor to consider investigating for insect artificial diets, is the effect of antimicrobial agents on the development and survival of larvae and pupae (Büyükgüzel & Yazgan, 2002; Roeder *et al.*, 2010). The current artificial diet for *S. noctilio* contains antimicrobial agents (streptomycin, sorbic acid,

methyl paraben, and sodium propionate). Some studies have found that antimicrobial agents can have deleterious effects on insect fitness (Singh & House, 1970; Alverson & Cohen, 2002). To ensure the production of high-quality *S. noctilio* individuals for research purposes and implementation in genetic pest management strategies, the optimal nutrient content and possible toxic effects of antimicrobial agents should be further investigated.

5. Statements and Declarations

The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

6. Acknowledgements

We are grateful to Josephine Queffelec, Leandri Klynsmith and Katy Termer for sharing preliminary observations on rearing of mature *S. noctilio* larvae on the *A. glabripennis* artificial diet as well as other diets. Glenda Britz is acknowledged for individual images created for use in the graphical abstract. This research was supported by Future Leaders-African Independent Research (FLAIR), grant number (FLR\R1\201229), which is a partnership between the African Academy of Sciences (AAS) and The Royal Society, supported by the Global Challenges Research Fund (GCRF). Further funding for this work was provided by the Tree Protection Co-operative Programme (TPCP) of the Forestry and Agricultural Biotechnology Institute (FABI), University of Pretoria.

7. References

Alverson, J. & Cohen, A.C. 2002. Effect of antifungal agents on biological fitness of *Lygus hesperus* (Heteroptera: Miridae). *Journal of Economic Entomology*, **95**: 256-260.

Andrew, R. & Patankar, N. 2010. The process of moulting during final emergence of the dragonfly *pantala flavescens* (Fabricius) (Anisoptera: Libellulidae). *Odonatologica*, **39**: 141-148.

Biedermann, P.H., Klepzig, K.D. & Taborsky, M. 2009. Fungus cultivation by ambrosia beetles: behavior and laboratory breeding success in three xyleborine species. *Environmental Entomology*, **38**: 1096-1105.

Büyükgüze, K. & Yazgan, S. 2002. Effects of antimicrobial agents on the survival and development of larvae of *Pimpla turionellae* L. (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae) reared on an artificial diet. *Turkish Journal of Zoology*, **26**: 112-119.

Castrillo, L.A., Griggs, M.H., Ranger, C.M., Reding, M.E. & Vandenberg, J.D. 2011. Virulence of commercial strains of *Beauveria bassiana* and *Metarhizium brunneum* (Ascomycota: Hypocreales) against adult *Xylosandrus germanus* (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) and impact on brood. *Biological Control*, **58**: 121-126.

Ciesla, W.M. 2003. European woodwasp: a potential threat to North America's conifer forests. *Journal of Forestry*, **101**: 18-23.

Cooperband, M.F., Stouthamer, R., Carrillo, D., Eskalen, A., Thibault, T., Cossé, A.A.,... Rugman-Jones, P.F. 2016. Biology of two members of the *Euwallacea fornicates* species complex (Coleoptera: Curculionidae: Scolytinae), recently invasive in the U.S.A., reared on an ambrosia beetle artificial diet. *Agricultural and Forest Entomology*, **18**: 223-237.

Coutts, M.P. 1969a. The mechanism of pathogenicity of *Sirex noctilio* on *Pinus radiata* L. Effects of the symbiotic fungus *Amylostereum* sp. (Thelophoraceae). *Australian Journal of Biological Sciences*, **22**: 915–924.

Coutts, M.P. 1969b. The mechanism of pathogenicity of *Sirex noctilio* on *Pinus radiata* II. Effects of *S. noctilio* mucus. *Australian Journal of Biological Sciences*, **22**: 1153–1161.

Coutts, M.P. & Dolezal, J.E. 1965. *Sirex noctilio*, its associated fungus, and some aspects of wood moisture content. *Australian Forestry Research*, **1**, 3-13.

De Viedma, M.G., Notario, A. & Baragaño, J.R. 1985. Laboratory rearing of lignicolous Coleoptera (Cerambycidae). *Journal of Economic Entomology*, **78**:1149-1150.

Fernández Ajó, A.A., Martínez, A.S., Villacide, J.M. & Corley, J.C. 2015. Behavioural response of the woodwasp *Sirex noctilio* to volatile emissions of its fungal symbiont. *Journal of Applied Entomology*, **139**: 654-659.

Fitza, K. N. E., Tabata, M., Kanzaki, N., Kimjura, K., Garnas, J. & Slippers, B. 2016. Host specificity and diversity of *Amylostereum* associated with Japanese siricids. *Fungal Ecology*, **24**: 76 – 81.

French, J.R.J. & Roeper, R.A. 1972. *In vitro* culture of the ambrosia beetle *Xyleborus dispar* (Coleoptera: Scolytidae) with its symbiotic fungus, *Ambrosiella hartigii*. *Annals of the Entomological Society of America*, **65**: 719-721.

Gruner, D.S. & Thompson, B.M. 2021. Nutritional ecology of *Sirex noctilio*. (In Hajek, A.E., Haavik, L.J. & F. M. Stephen, eds. *Biology and Ecology of Sirex noctilio* in North America. Morgantown, West Virginia: USDA Forest Service. p. 38-48).

Hoebeker, E., Haugen, D.A. & Haack, R. 2005. *Sirex noctilio*: discovery of a Palearctic siricid woodwasp in New York. *Newsletter of the Michigan Entomological Society*, **50**: 24-25.

Hurley, B.P., Slippers, B. & Wingfield, M.J. 2007. A comparison of control results for the alien invasive woodwasp, *Sirex noctilio*, in the southern hemisphere. *Agricultural and Forest Entomology*, **9**: 159-171.

Keena, M.A. 2005. Pourable artificial diet for rearing *Anoplophora glabripennis* (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) and methods to optimize larval survival and synchronize development. *Annals of the Entomological Society of America*, **98**: 536-547.

Lake Maner, M., Hanula, J.L. & Kristine Braman, S. 2013. Rearing redbay ambrosia beetle, *Xyleborus glabratus* (Coleoptera: Curculionidae: Scolytinae), on semi-artificial media. *Florida Entomologist*, **96**: 1042-1051.

Leftwich, P.T., Spurgin, L.G., Harvey-Samuel, T., Thomas, C.J.E., Paladino, L.C., Edgington, M.P. & Alphey, L. 2021. Genetic pest management and the background genetics of release strains. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B*, **376**: 20190805.

Lindig, O.H., Hedin, P.A. & Poe, W.E. 1981. Amino acids in pecan weevil, southwestern corn borer and tarnished plant bug, and at their feeding sites. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology Part A: Physiology*, **68**: 261-263.

Madden, J.L. 1981. Egg and larval development in the woodwasp, *Sirex noctilio* F. *Australian Journal of Zoology*, **29**: 493-506.

Menocal, O., Cruz, L.F., Kendra, P.E., Crane, J.H., Ploetz, R.C. & Carrillo, D. 2017. Rearing *Xyleborus volvulus* (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) on media containing sawdust from avocado or silkbay, with or without *Raffaelea lauricola* (Ophiostomatales: Ophiostomataceae). *Environmental Entomology*, **46**: 1275-1283.

Mlonyeni, X.O., Wingfield, M. J., Greeff, J. M., Wingfield, B. D. & Slippers, B. 2018. Genetic diversity of *Amylostereum areolatum*, the fungal symbiont of the invasive woodwasp *Sirex noctilio* in South Africa. *Forest Pathology*, **48** p. e12449

Morales-Ramos, J.A., Rojas, M.G., Coudron, T.A., Huynh, M.P., Zou, D. & Shelby, K.S. 2023. Artificial diet development for entomophagous arthropods. (In Morales-Ramos J.A., Rojas, M.G. & Shapiro-Ilan, D.I., eds. Mass production of beneficial organisms: Invertebrates and entomopathogens. Second edition ed. Massachusetts, United States: Academic Press. p. 233-260).

- Ngomane, N.C., Pieterse, E., Woods, M.J. & Conlong, D.E. 2022. Formulation of artificial diets for mass-rearing *Eldana saccharina* Walker (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) using the carcass milling technique. *Insects*, **13**: 316.
- Pinto, J.R.L., Torres, A.F., Truzzi, C.C., Vieira, N.F., Vacari, A.M. & De Bortoli, S.A. 2019. Artificial corn-based diet for rearing *Spodoptera frugiperda* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). *Journal of Insect Science*, **19**: 1-8.
- Roeder, K.A., Kuriachan, I., Vinson, S.B. & Behmer, S.T. 2010. Evaluation of a microbial inhibitor in artificial diets of a generalist caterpillar, *Heliothis virescens*. *Journal of Insect Science*, **10**:197.
- Rogers, D.J., Lewthwaite, S.E. & Dentener, P.R. 2002. Rearing huhu beetle larvae, *Prionoplus reticularis* (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) on artificial diet. *New Zealand Journal of Zoology*, **29**: 303-310.
- Ryan, K. & Hurley, B.P. 2012. Life history and biology of *Sirex noctilio*. (In Slippers, B., De Groot, P. & Wingfield, M.J., eds. The Sirex woodwasp and its fungal symbiont:. Dordrecht: Springer. p. 15-30).
- Sahayaraj, K. & Balasubramanian, R. 2009. Biological control potential of artificial diet and insect hosts reared *Rhynocoris marginatus*(Fab.) on three pests. *Archives Of Phytopathology And Plant Protection*, **42**: 238-247.
- Saunders, J.L. & Knoke, J.K. 1967. Diets for rearing the ambrosia beetle *Xyleborus ferrugineus* (Fabricius) *in vitro*. *Science*, **157**: 460-463.
- Sharma, T., Dedes, J. & Macquarrie, C.J.K. 2017. A modified technique for rearing wood boring insects permits visualization of larval development. *The Journal of the Entomological Society of Ontario*, **147**:7-14.
- Singh, P. & House, H.L. 1970. Antimicrobial agents: Their detrimental effects on size of an insect, *Agria affins*. *The Canadian Entomologist*, **102**: 1340-1344.

Spradbery, J.P. 1973. A comparative study of the phytotoxic effects of siricid woodwasps on conifers. *Annals of Applied Biology*, **75**: 309-320.

Termer, K.E. 2014. Biotic and abiotic determinants of resource quality for the larvae of the European woodwasp, *Sirex noctilio*. Pretoria: University of Pretoria. (Dissertation – MSc).

Thompson, B.M., Grebenok, R.J., Behmer, S.T. & Gruner, D.S. 2013. Microbial symbionts shape the sterol profile of the xylem-feeding woodwasp, *Sirex noctilio*. *Journal of Chemical Ecology*, **39**: 129-139.

Thompson, B.M., Bodart, J., McEwen, C. & Gruner, D.S. 2014. Adaptations for symbiont-mediated external digestion in *Sirex noctilio* (Hymenoptera: Siricidae). *Annals of the Entomological Society of America*, **107**: 453-460.

Van der Merwe, E., Slippers, B. & Dittrich-Schröder, G., 2023. Mechanical Egg Activation and Rearing of First Instar Larvae of *Sirex noctilio* (Hymenoptera: Siricidae). *Insects*, **14**, 931. <https://doi.org/10.3390/insects14120931>

White, B.H. & Ewer, J. 2014. Neural and hormonal control of postecdysial behaviors in insects. *Annual Review of Entomology*, **59**: 363-381.

Woods, M.J., Conlong, D.E., Ngomane, N., Gillespie, D.Y., Hoffman, L.C. & Pieterse, E. 2020. The development of an improved artificial diet for the mass rearing of *Eldana saccharina* Walker (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae). *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture* **100**: 4678-4687.

Yousuf, F., Carnegie, A.J., Bedding, R.A., Bashford, R., Nicol, H.I. & Gurr, G.M. 2014. Effect of temperature on woodwasp (*Sirex noctilio* F.) development and parasitism by the entomopathogenic nematode, *Deladenus siricidicola*. *Biological Control*, **79**: 67-74.

Zapata, R., Specty, O., Grenier, S., Febvay, G., Pageaux, J.F., Delobel, B. & Castane, C. 2005. Carcass analysis to improve a meat-based diet for the artificial rearing of the predatory mirid bug *Dicyphus tamaninii*. *Archives of Insect Biochemistry and Physiology*, **60**: 84-92.

Figure 1. Pine log storage and log splitting. **(A)** Large pine logs stored upright in an outdoor double-netted cage. **(B)** Pine logs cross-stacked and watered with a garden pressure sprayer. **(C)** A log split into the smallest manageable piece. **(D)** Larvae and pupae transferred to a Petri dish after extraction from logs; Rearing methods for Diet A. **(E)** Cake saver with larvae placed in Petri dishes and Falcon tubes filled with Diet A. **(F)** Pupae placed in holes drilled in a pine log and sealed with Diet A. **(G)** Pupa wrapped in printing paper; Rearing methods for Diet C. **(H)** Four vials filled with plain wheat/rice diet (left) and four vials filled with wheat/rice/pine sawdust mixture (right). **(I)** Closer view of Diet C in plastic vials; Rearing of larvae on Diet A. **(J)** Fungal contamination on Diet A1 after five days. **(K)** *Amylostereum areolatum* growth next to larvae. **(L)** Swollen lower abdominal segments of a larva that was covered with diet. **(M)** Small balls of diet suspected to be larval frass. **(N)** Adult female with deformed wings reared in a Petri dish. **(O)** Fungal overgrowth on pupa wrapped in paper; Rearing of larvae on Diet B. **(P)** Microbial contamination on Diet B in Petri dishes; Rearing of larvae on Diet C. **(Q)** Fungal contamination and overgrowth in vials containing Diet C. **(R)** Deformed adult male that emerged on Diet C.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Table S1: Pine log collection information

Province	Batch	Date	Plantation	<i>Pinus</i> sp.	Age
Western Cape	1	February 2021	MTO Garcia, Riversdale	<i>Pinus radiata</i>	28
	2	February 2022	MTO Garcia, Riversdale	<i>P. radiata</i>	18
	3	January 2023	MTO Garcia, Riversdale	<i>P. radiata</i>	24
Mpumalanga	1	June 2021	SAPPI, Sabie	<i>Pinus patula</i>	12-16
	2	October 2021	SAPPI, Sabie	<i>P. patula</i>	12-16
	3	July 2022	SAPPI, Sabie	<i>P. patula</i>	12-16

Table S2: Ingredients for *Anoplophora glabripennis* artificial diet adapted for *Sirex noctilio*

Ingredient	Manufacturer	Diet A- NRC*	Diet A1	Diet A2	Diet A3	Diet A4
Distilled water		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Agar	Sigma-Aldrich	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Group 1						
Raw wheat germ	Sigma-Aldrich	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Torula yeast powder	Sigma-Aldrich	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Group 2						
Wesson salt mixture	MP Biomedicals	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Sorbic acid	Natural Resources Canada	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓
Methyl paraben	Natural Resources Canada	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓
Sucrose (or household sugar)	Natural Resources Canada	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Casein from bovine milk	Sigma-Aldrich	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Sodium propionate	Natural Resources Canada	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓
Group 3						
Cholesterol	Sigma grade ≥ 99%, Sigma-Aldrich	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Wheatgerm oil	Essentially Natural	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Group 4						
Choline chloride	≥98% Sigma-Aldrich	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Vanderzant vitamin mixture for insects	Sigma-Aldrich	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Vitamin A beadlets	Natural Resources Canada	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Group 5						
Alpha cellulose	Sigma-Aldrich	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Group 6						
Streptomycin sulfate salt	Sigma-Aldrich	x	x	✓	✓	✓
SABAX pour water		x	x	✓	✓	✓
Group 7						
Autoclaved pine sawdust/shavings		x	✓	x	✓	✓
Group 8						
<i>Amylostereum areolatum</i>		x	✓	✓	✓	x

*Diet A-NRC = Diet Natural Resources Canada